

A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON EFFECT OF ALTERNATE DRYING AND WETTING CYCLES ON STABILITY OF LIME TREATED BLACK COTTON (BC)SOIL

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Abstract

Lime treatment induces several time-dependent physico-chemical processes that result in the bonding of soil particles. This treatment results in improved soil strength and reduced swelling properties of clay soil. However, these positive effects of lime-treatment could be affected by weathering action in the very long term. This paper presents the effects of successive wetting and drying cycles on the hydro-mechanical properties of a lime-treated clayey soil. Black cotton soil samples treated with quicklime were subjected to alternate wetting and drying cycles through saturation and thermostatically controlled drying. The effect of quicklime dosage and curing time on strength deterioration of soil samples subjected to AWD were considered in the study. The results indicated enhanced swelling properties of the material and a progressive loss of strength with increasing number of AWD cycles. The extent of the degradation is directly related to the amount of added quicklime and the amplitude of the AWD cycles. Studies indicated that strength lime stabilized BC soil significantly when subjected to successive wetting-drying cycles. Thus, the weathering effects should be accounted for the long-term design of treated soil structure.

Keywords: BC Soil, Lime Stabilization, Wetting-Drying Cycles, Strength Deterioration.

1. INTRODUCTION

India has large geographical area of 3,287,240 sq. km and population of 125 million which demands for vast network of structures and road. Four major types of soils cover 70 to 80% of total land area, which includes alluvial soil, red earth, black cotton soil and desert soil. Black Cotton (BC) soils are inorganic soils and covers an area of about 5,20,000 square km in India. The construction of durable roads on BC soils always presented serious problems to engineers. Black cotton soil has high swelling and shrinkage properties.

BC soil is quite strong in dry state and possesses high swelling during wetting with extremely low bearing capacity when it is wet. Volume change in clays can be significant and occur as the moisture content changes. The volumetric changes cause instability of the road, resulting in an uneven pavement surface, longitudinal ruts, detrimental cracking and, ultimately causes premature deterioration. BC soils in the natural state do not present adequate geotechnical properties as a subgrade material.

Solutions to the problems presented by BC soil as a subgrade material include excavating and replacing the thickness of clay with a select fill material and increasing the base thickness layer to decrease subgrade stresses and minimize moisture changes. Both solutions are inherently expensive and require disposal or the use of large quantity of locally available materials. The

most economical way of addressing strength deficiencies is through modifying the virgin material using soil stabilization techniques. Soil stabilization is referred to as a method of increasing load-bearing capacity and stability of soil.

Over the past decades, significant research has been conducted to develop and present various methods to stabilize the soft and expansive soils. For the long-term performance of pavements is very essential to evaluate the suitability of the soil stabilization technique adopted both in terms of initial cost and life time maintenance cost.

It is also essential to ensure the behavior of the stabilized soil shall not be altered to the changes in the environmental conditions throughout the design life of the stabilized soil. Portland cement and lime have been used successfully for stabilization of BC soil subgrade. Lime as a soil stabilizer is an effective option due to its availability and cost-effectiveness. ASTM D-6276 provides guidelines for estimating the minimum soil-lime proportion which yields a pH of 12.4 signifies the requirement for lime for soil stabilization.

From the studies it was seen that a minimum lime content of 7% yielded a stable pH of 12.4 which is considered as optimum lime content (Srinivas F. Chitragar et. al. 2021). In previous studies, many researchers investigated the effects of lime stabilization on the strength and swelling characteristics of clayey soils but few have been carried out on the durability of the material, in particular the effect of alternate wetting and drying (AWD) and freeze-thaw. The unconfined compressive strength of soil samples could be used as indicator of durability and strength properties of natural and stabilized soils under AWD.

A. Aldaood et al. (2014) showed that the problematic soil stabilized with 3% lime is subjected to different curing times of up to 28 days and exposed to 6 wetting–drying cycles. Results showed that the strength of the compacted soil samples increased with curing time, while the wetting–drying cycles had a detrimental effect on the compressive strength. Anca Hotinean et al. (2015) investigated the impact of F-T cycles on the mechanical properties of two types of plastic soils, stabilized with lime.

The results indicate that UCS increased significantly with curing time and after subjecting the materials to F-T action, the damage was found in the form of cracks in lime-stabilized soil samples. Glenn Strysteen et al. investigated the impact of 12 freeze-thaw cycles on the mechanical properties of stabilized soils using wide range of stabilizing products. Results indicate that freeze-thaw cycles reduce the unconfined compressive strength of all the test specimens by 10%.

In the present study BC soil is stabilized using hydrated lime and efforts are made to evaluate the effects of AWD on the strength properties of lime stabilized BC soil.

2. MATERIALS AND TESTING METHOD

2.1 Materials

The raw black cotton soil was collected from Adavisomapura Village, Gadhadar District, Karnataka. The soil sample was allowed for air drying for a week and then grinded into

required size in a soil mill near Peenya, Bangalore. The various physical and geotechnical index properties of the soil were investigated in laboratory and are listed in Table 1. Based on the Atterberg limit values the soil was classified as high plasticity clay (CH) as per Unified Soil Classification System (USCS).

Commercially available hydrated lime $[Ca(OH)_2]$ obtained from local suppliers has been used as a stabilizing agent. Properties of lime used are as shown in Table 2.

Table 1: Physical and Index Properties of Soil

Index Property	Results Obtained	Technical Reference
Specific Gravity	2.11	IS:2720(Part 3)-1989 [11]
Grain Size Distribution		IS:2720(part 4)-2006 [12]
Gravel	0%	
Sand	7%	
Silt & Clay	93%	
Atterberg Limits		IS:2720(Part 5)-2006 [13]
Liquid Limit	82%	
Plastic Limit	68.57%	
Plasticity Index	13.43%	
Soil Classification	CH	USS
Free Swell Index	33.33%	IS 2720: Part 40:1977
Standard Compaction		IS 2720: Part 16: 1987
Optimum Moisture Content	26.5%	
Maximum Dry Density	1.484 g/cc	
CBR	1.253%	
Unconfined Compression Strength	0.15 MPa	IS 2720: Part 10: 1991

Table 2: Properties of Hydrated Lime

Chemical Constituents	Percentage
CaO	>82.2
MgO	<0.49
Fe ₂ O ₃	<2.1
Al ₂ O ₃	<1.5
SiO ₃	<2.49
Na ₂ O	0.3-0.5
CO ₂	<5.1
CaCO ₃	<9

2.2 Sample Preparation

In order to access the effects of alternate wetting and drying (AWD) on lime stabilized BC soil, the soil to be tested is first stabilized using hydrated lime. The studies proven that by using minimum 7% lime content of yielded a stable pH of 12.4 which is considered as optimum lime content.

To prepare the samples, the soil was treated with 7% of hydrated lime and thoroughly mixed in a dry state until the mixture had a homogeneous and uniform appearance. The soil-lime mixture is wetted to optimum moisture content and remixed thoroughly.

The wet mixture was then kept in plastic bags to allow mellowing for a duration of 1 hour. After that, the soil sample was statically compacted at optimum moisture content and maximum dry unit weight inside a cylindrical mould, with a final dimension the soil sample of 50 mm in diameter and 100 mm in height. The soil sample was immediately extracted from the mould and kept in plastic bags till testing to avoid significant variations in moisture content.

2.3 Curing on Lime-stabilized soil

Curing is an important factor in achieving good stabilized lime-soil mix. Strength development with respect to curing period is crucial in study of behavior of stabilized soil as strength gain of lime-soil mixture depends on continuing hydration/pozzolanic reaction with time. To illustrate strength development of lime treated BC soil, the prepared samples were sealed inside polythene bags and cured in a desiccator to prevent for periods of 1, 3, 7, 14, and 28 days after which they were subjected to UCS test to access strength development.

Fig 1: Preparation of Lime-soil mixture

Fig 2: Curing of prepared samples in desiccators

2.4 Alternate Wetting and Drying Process

After 28 days of curing lime stabilised soil specimens were subjected to several cycles of alternate wetting and drying cycle as per ASTM D 559(6). Each cycle of AWD consists of 1 day wetting by completely immersing the soil samples in water at room temperature Figure 14, followed by drying the samples for 3 days of.

The soil samples were allowed to drying using natural drying at room temperature/ controlled temperature drying at a temperature of 27°C. The UCS of the soil samples was determined in the drying state after the completion of each cycles.

Fig 3: Wetting Process

Fig 4: Controlled Drying Process

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effect of additives on soil properties

The soil stabilized with 7% of lime is subjected to compaction test to determine OMC and MDD.

To compare strength improvement of stabilized soil, the soil samples were tested for unconfined compressive strength (UCS) and CBR value.

The physical properties of untreated and lime stabilized BC soil are as tabulated in Table: 3

Table 3: Physical properties of untreated and lime-stabilized BC soil

Particulars	Untreated Soil	Soil treated with 7% Lime
Optimum Moisture Content, %	26.5	26
Maximum Dry Density, g/cc	1.484	1.884
CBR, %	1.253	4.96
UCS, kN/m ²	148.87	311.67

The study reveals that addition of lime to an expansive soil, increases the maximum dry density. The unconfined compressive strength (UCS) and CBR value of BC Soil increases by stabilizing the BC soil with 7% optimum dosage of hydrated lime.

3.2 Effect of curing on strength of lime stabilized soil

Lime stabilized BC soil cured in a desiccator for of 1, 3, 7, 14, and 28 days after which they were subjected to UCS test to access strength development and results are reported in Table 4 & Figure 5

Table 4: Effect of Curing Period on UCS Value

Curing Days	UCS Value kN/m ²	
	Untreated Soil	Lime-soil Mixture
1 Day	160.98	370.09
3 Days	200.60	427.77
7 Days	220.33	507.73
15 Days	235.86	818.20
28 Days	245.43	1102.28

Fig 5: Effect of AWD Cycle on Unconfined Compressive Strength of BC Soil

The strength of lime stabilized BC soil increases with curing period. The rate of strength increment is considerably low up to 15 days and increases thereafter, indicating that at least 15 days of curing is required to achieve greater strength for lime treated BC Soil.

3.3 Effect of AWD on lime stabilized soil

The soil samples after 28 days of curing are subjected to alternate wetting and drying cycles to assess extent of strength deterioration, which is measured by subjecting soil samples to UCS test after each AWD cycle. The crack formation pattern and strength of soil specimens after each cycle of AWD is as shown in the Table 5, Figure 7(a) & (b) and Figure 8(a), (b), (c) and (d) respectively.

Table 5: Effect of AWD cycles on strength of Lime-stabilizes soil

Particulars	UCS in kN/m ²	
	0% Lime	7% Lime
28 Days curing	245.428	1102.28
1 st AWD Cycle	230.60	1067.00
2 nd AWD Cycle	-	918.24
3 rd AWD Cycle	-	393.07

Fig 6: Strength Deterioration of lime stabilized BC soil subjected to AWD Cycle

a) Crack formation after 1st Cycle

b) Failed specimen during 2nd cycle of wetting

Fig 7: Pattern of crack formation and specimen failure in Untreated BC soil

Fig 8: Pattern of crack formation after each cycle of AWD in Lime Stabilized BC soil

When subjected to 1st AWD cycles the UCS is found to have increased very marginally, but after subjecting the specimens to 2nd AWD cycle, the UCS was observed remain as that of 28 days curing of treated specimen.

Lime treated BC soil is found to have lost more than 50% of its strength by the end of 3rd cycle when compared with the strength at the end of 28 days curing. The soil is found to have collapsed even before the test when the specimens were subjected to 4th AWD cycle.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The findings of the study demonstrate the impact of alternate wetting drying cycles on the durability and mainly on the mechanical property of lime stabilized black cotton soil. Lime stabilized black cotton soil exhibits higher CBR and UCS value compared to untreated soil before subjecting it to AWD cycles.

From the first cycle of AWD, observed the stability samples decreases gradually resulting in strength deuteriation in the all the samples tested. Lime treated BC soil is found to have lost more than 50% of its strength by the end of 3rd cycle and the specimens were collapsed even before it is subjected to 4th cycle indicating that, the moisture absorption and successive drying has a variable effect on lime treated black cotton soil. Thus, the weathering effects should be accounted for the long-term design of treated soil structure.

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